

Back of the envelope estimate of the climate impact of the Nord Stream 1 and 2 sabotage – revised version

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Revisions: The content of the note was changed 2022-10-07 according to recent information. One of the four pipelines is intact, i.e., there are four ruptures affecting three pipelines. Further, a short discussion about the climate impact of non-methane hydrocarbons (such as ethane and propane) potentially present in the leaked natural gas has been added to the note (footnote 6).

Questions:

- How large are the methane emissions from the leakage?
- How large are the CO₂-equivalent emissions from the leakage?
- What are the temperature consequences of the leakage and how do they compare with those caused by Swedish territorial emissions?

Approach: Media have reported that both Nord Stream 1 (consisting of two pipelines) and 2 (also consisting of two pipelines) have been sabotaged. There appears to be four ruptures affecting three pipelines. Each pipeline is about 1200 km long, and has an inner diameter of about 1.15 m. We assume that they are full of natural gas at a pressure of about 200 bar (in line with the pipeline pressure under normal working conditions, as reported by DN¹ and Nord Stream²). If the actual pressure is lower, the pipelines contain less natural gas, and the climate impact will be smaller. Hence, our estimate is likely at the upper end of the actual average pressure of the pipelines.

Pipelines natural gas (sometimes referred to as dry gas) is dominated by methane (CH₄), but can also contain other compounds, primarily other hydrocarbons such as ethane (C₂H₆) and propane (C₃H₈). The potential non-methane hydrocarbons are also (indirect) greenhouse gases. These gases have a small direct greenhouse effect, but through chemical reactions in the atmosphere they prolong the lifetime of methane, causes tropospheric ozone as well as carbon dioxide.³ Through these mechanisms they have a strong greenhouse effect, which is, on a per mole basis, close to that of methane. We assume for now that all the natural gas that leaks is pure methane but give an estimate below of much the results may have differed if we explicitly considered the different types of hydrocarbons (see footnote 6).

How much methane is in each pipeline? We use the ideal gas law, $n = PV/RT$, where n is the number of moles of CH₄ (or combination of different compounds), P is the pressure [Pa], V is the volume [m³], T is the temperature [K] (we assume that $T = 278$

¹ <https://www.dn.se/varlden/expertter-om-nord-stream-lackorna-man-blir-misstanksam/>

² <https://www.nord-stream.com/download/document/10/?language=en> and <https://archive.ph/20130427110540/http://www.nord-stream.com/sv/press-information/pressmeddelanden/nord-streams-naturgasledning-ett-steg-naermare-faerdigstaellande-330/>

³ <https://doi.org/10.1002/asl.804>

K at the bottom of the Baltic Sea), and R is the ideal gas constant (about 8.3 [m³*Pa*K⁻¹*mol⁻¹]).

Volume of gas per pipeline, $V=1\ 200\ 000\ [m]^3 \cdot 1.15^2\ [m^2] \cdot \pi/4 = 1.25\ Mm^3$ at a pressure at 200 bar.

$n=200 \cdot 1 \cdot 10^5 \cdot 1.25 \cdot 10^6 / (8.3 \cdot 278) = 10.8$ Gmol of CH₄ (or other compounds) per pipeline.⁴

The molar mass for CH₄ is 16 g/mol => M=16 [g/mol]* 10.8 [Gmol]=173 Gg of CH₄=0.173 million tons (Mt) CH₄ per pipeline.

The three pipelines will consequently have released about 0.52 MtCH₄ when they have been fully emptied (given the assumptions stated above).

The 100-year global warming potential (also known as GWP-100, which is the greenhouse gas metric adopted within the UNFCCC⁵) for methane is 29.8 in IPCC AR6.

Hence, the CO₂ equivalent emissions are 0.54*29.8=15.5 MtCO₂-equivalents if all pipelines leak all methane they contain, if the average pressure is 200 bar, and if we assume that the ideal gas law applies.⁶

To put the numbers into context: Global anthropogenic emissions of CH₄ are about 350 MtCH₄ => the leakage is less than 0.2% of global anthropogenic CH₄ emissions. Swedish annual territorial emissions (excluding LULUCF and international bunkering) of greenhouse gases are about 50 MtCO₂-equivalents => the leakage is about 30% of Swedish annual greenhouse emissions. Further, the annual variability in methane emissions from wetlands are in the order of a few single digits of MtCH₄/year (<https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13726>) => the leakage is smaller than annual variability in methane emissions from wetlands.

⁴ The use of the ideal gas law likely led to an underestimate of the number of moles. More accurate estimates should include the compressibility factor of methane, see for example section 2.5.1 in <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1221714/FULLTEXT01.pdf>. Our estimate likely underestimates the numbers of mole with about 20%-30% given the assumed pressure in the pipeline of 200 bar.

⁵ <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/transparency-and-reporting/methods-for-climate-change-transparency/common-metrics>

⁶ We have assumed that the leaked natural gas is pure methane. However, if we assume that the gas is 90% methane, 9% ethane and 1% propane on a molar basis (a rather typical example of dry gas) the results would have been slightly different. The mass content of the estimated leakage would be 0.47 Mton Methane, 0.088 Mton Ethane, 0.0114 Mton Propane given the used assumptions on volume, pressure etc. According to <https://doi.org/10.1002/asl.804> the GWP-100 for Ethane is 10.2 and for Propane it is 9.5. In addition, we need to add the amount of CO₂ that is caused when the gases are broken down, since that is not included in the GWP estimates for ethane and propane presented in that study (<https://doi.org/10.1002/asl.804>). That would add 2.9 to the GWP-100 for Ethane, and 3 to the GWP-100 for Propane. Hence, GWP-100 for Ethane is 13.1, and for Propane it is 12.5 when including the heating they cause after the gases has broken down to CO₂. Hence, the CO₂-equivalent emissions of the leak would in this case (90% Methane, 9% Ethane and 1% Propane) be 0.47*29.80 + 0.088*13.1 + 0.0114*12.5=15.1 Mton CO₂-equivalents. Hence, about 3% lower than if the natural gas was pure methane. However, note that this climate impact of Ethane and Propane would not have been reported national greenhouse gas statistics, although the climate impact would be real, but uncertain.

Disclaimer: The estimate of the amount of methane in the pipelines are based on data reported in the media over the last days as well as other information easily available on the Internet. Those numbers may not be correct. Also, we do not know if all the methane contained in the pipelines will leak out into the Baltic Sea and reach the atmosphere. Finally, the ideal gas law is not exact at pressures as high as 200 bar.

Temperature impact calculation

We use a simple climate model for estimating the impact of these emissions on the global average surface temperature. The model is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/5957222>. The model, and its parametrization, is based on the model used for estimating metrics such as GWP and GTP in IPCC AR6.

We estimate the climate impact of the leaked methane based on the numbers in the previous section. In the estimation of the temperature consequences of the leaked methane, we consider that when fossil CH₄ is oxidized in the atmosphere it also contributes to atmospheric CO₂. Further, the model considers the different perturbation lifetimes of CH₄, N₂O and CO₂. The atmospheric lifetime for CH₄ is relatively short (11.8 years), while the lifetimes of N₂O and CO₂ are considerably larger. The model also considers the radiative forcing of each gas, including indirect effects (such as methane emissions impacts on tropospheric ozone – O₃). Finally, the model estimates the impact on global average surface temperature, while accounting for the thermal inertia caused by the oceans.

The temperature outcome of the model is very uncertain due to large uncertainties in the equilibrium climate sensitivity, various feedbacks, and the time scales of the thermal inertia.

The numbers used for Swedish territorial emissions are collected from the official statistics⁷.

The analyzed cases compare the temperature impact of emissions from the leakage to Swedish emissions during one full year. The considered cases are:

1. Leakage of methane from one pipeline.
2. Leakage of methane from three identical pipelines.
3. Swedish greenhouse gases emissions (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) from domestic transport for 2019.
4. Swedish greenhouse gases emissions (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) from territorial emissions (excluding LULUCF) for 2019.
5. The impact if the estimated methane leakage from the three pipelines would have been combusted and emitted as CO₂.

⁷ <http://www.scb.se/mi0107>

Figure 1. The estimated temperature impact of the leaked methane from Nord Stream 1 and 2, and its comparison to the impact of Swedish annual greenhouse gas emissions.

As seen in the figure the potential near-term climate impact of the leakage is comparable to the climate impact of one year of Swedish greenhouse gas emissions. During the coming decade, the estimated temperature impact of the leakage is about 10% smaller than the temperature impact of one year of Swedish emissions, and after that the impact of the leakage drops rather rapidly in comparison to that caused by one year of Swedish Emissions. The reason for this is that methane is a strong greenhouse gas relative to carbon dioxide, which accounts for the majority of Swedish annual emissions, but methane has a relatively short atmospheric lifetime in comparison to carbon dioxide. Methane is being broken down rapidly in the atmosphere, while carbon dioxide stays in the atmosphere for thousands of years.